

ANALYSIS OF FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE CUSTOMER LOYALTY IN WAPRES COFFEE

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the factors that influence customer loyalty at Wapres Coffee, focusing on Generation Z customers. The factors studied include product quality, service quality, price, and cafe atmosphere. This study uses a quantitative approach with a survey method. The research sample consisted of 100 respondents selected using a purposive sampling technique, with the criteria of having made at least two purchases and being among Generation Z. Data collection was carried out through a structured questionnaire with a 5-point Likert scale. Data analysis used Structural Equation Modeling based on Partial Least Square (PLS) with the help of SmartPLS 3.0. The results showed that product quality ($t = 2.429$; $p = 0.015$) and cafe atmosphere ($t = 2.108$; $p = 0.036$) had a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty. Conversely, service quality ($t = 0.996$; $p = 0.320$) and price ($t = 1.226$; $p = 0.221$) were not proven to have a significant effect on customer loyalty. Product quality is the most dominant factor in shaping customer loyalty, with a path coefficient of 0.351. An R-squared value of 0.727 indicates that the four independent variables can explain 72.7% of the variation in customer loyalty. This study confirms that consistent product quality and a comfortable cafe atmosphere are key to building and maintaining Generation Z customer loyalty at Wapres Coffee.

Keywords: Loyalty, Product Quality, Service Quality, Price, Cafe Atmosphere

INTRODUCTION

Customer loyalty is a key factor in business sustainability in the service sector, particularly the cafe and restaurant industry, which faces increasingly high levels of competition. Customer loyalty is reflected not only in repeat purchasing behavior but also in customers' commitment to continue choosing a brand and their willingness to recommend it to others (Kotler and Keller 2016) and (Hair et al. 2019). In the cafe industry, customer loyalty plays a strategic role because it can create long-term revenue stability and reduce dependence on short-term promotional strategies.

The development of the coffee shop industry in Indonesia shows a significant growth trend in line with the rise of coffee drinking culture and changes in urban lifestyles. Generation Z has become a dominant consumer segment in this industry. Generation Z's characteristics, closely linked to digital technology, social activities, and a preference for social experiences, make cafes not only places to consume but also spaces for social interaction (Priporas, Stylos, and Fotiadis 2021). Several studies have shown that Generation Z tends to prefer cafes with aesthetic concepts, attractive interior designs, and an atmosphere conducive to social media activity (Kim and Lee 2020).

However, the phenomenon at Wapres Coffee shows a different trend. While Wapres Coffee doesn't promote a modern aesthetic design concept or a visually themed cafe, it remains popular among young people, including Generation Z. This phenomenon is interesting to study because it indicates that customer loyalty isn't always determined by visual appeal, but rather by other functional and substantive factors. Based on visitor data listed in the research document, Wapres Coffee shows an increasing trend in visitor numbers over the past six months. This data is presented in the following table.

Table 1.
Number of Visitors to Wapres Coffee (Last 6 Months of 2025)

MONTH	NUMBER OF VISITORS
JULY	1320
AUGUST	1345
SEPTEMBER	1410
OCTOBER	1465
NOVEMBER	1510
DECEMBER	1580

Source: Internal observation data of Vice President Coffee (2025)

The data in the table shows a consistent upward trend in the number of visitors. This increase indicates a tendency for repeat customers, which is an indicator of customer loyalty. This condition strengthens the assumption that Wapres Coffee is able to build customer loyalty even though it does not rely on the aesthetic cafe concept that is currently trending among Generation Z. Theoretically, customer loyalty in the cafe industry is influenced by several key factors, including product quality, service quality, price, and cafe atmosphere. Product quality reflects the cafe's ability to serve drinks and food with consistent flavors and in accordance with customer expectations. Research (Agustia 2022) and (Rahmayoga and Wiwoho 2025) prove that product quality has a positive and significant influence on customer loyalty in culinary businesses.

In addition to product quality, service quality is an important factor in building customer loyalty. Friendly, fast, and responsive service can create a positive experience that encourages customers to make repeat purchases (Hidayati, Purnomo, and Sudjimat 2023), (Soerjanto, Priyanto, and Rahayu 2024). In the context of Wapres Coffee, service quality is reflected in direct interactions between employees and customers that are informal but familiar, thus creating emotional closeness (Sinaga, Tampubolon, and Sinaga 2023).

Price also influences customer loyalty, especially in the Generation Z segment, which prioritizes the appropriateness of price and perceived benefits. (Konuk 2021) stated that perceived price fairness influences customer loyalty through the formation of perceived value. However, several studies have shown that when product and service quality meet expectations, price is not always the dominant factor in determining loyalty (Wijaya and Tjokrosaputro 2024).

Cafe atmosphere in this study is understood as functional comfort that includes cleanliness, layout, lighting, and the general atmosphere of the cafe, not merely visual aesthetics. (Kim and Lee 2020) explained that cafe atmosphere can influence customer emotions and contribute to loyalty, although the influence is contextual. For Wapres Coffee customers, a comfortable atmosphere that supports hanging out activities is considered more important than mere visual aspects.

Relevant international research conducted by Ferdian, Anuar, and Muhamad Fadzli (2023) in Malaysia found that product and service quality are key determinants of coffee shop customer satisfaction and revisit intentions. Furthermore, a study by Hwang and Choe (2022) in the *Journal of Business Research* showed that young consumers tend to build loyalty based on perceived core quality and functional value.

Based on the empirical phenomena and the results of previous research, it can be concluded that customer loyalty at Wapres Coffee is potentially influenced by product quality, service quality, price, and cafe atmosphere. Therefore, this study focuses on analyzing the factors that influence Generation Z customer loyalty at Wapres Coffee. The purpose of this study is to examine the influence of product quality, service quality, price, and cafe atmosphere on customer loyalty at Wapres Coffee.

METHOD

This study employed a quantitative approach with a survey method supported by primary and secondary data. The quantitative approach was chosen because the study aimed to objectively and measurably test the influence of independent variables on the dependent variable based on numerical data.

Population and Research Sample

The population in this study is all customers of Wapres Coffee and Resto. conducted visits during the research period. Since the population size is known, the sample size was determined using the Slovin formula with an error

rate (e) of 10%. Based on these calculations, the sample size used in this study was 100 respondents. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling, with the criteria being that respondents had made at least two purchases and were young people, such as Gen-Z, at Wapres Coffee and Resto.

Data collection technique

Data collection in this study was conducted using primary and secondary data. Primary data was obtained directly from respondents through a survey method using a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed to Wapres Coffee and Resto customers who met the respondent criteria, namely having made at least two purchases and being among young people such as Gen-Z. The questionnaire instrument was compiled based on indicators that have been used and validated in previous studies related to cafe and restaurant customer loyalty (Hidayati, Purnomo, and Sudjimat 2023); (Ferdian, Anuar, and Muhamad Fadzli 2023); (Wijaya and Tjokrosaputro 2024). The measurement scale used was a 5-point Likert scale referring to (Sugiyono 2019), without using a neutral category, with the aim of obtaining a more assertive respondent attitude towards each statement.

Secondary data was obtained from internal documents of Wapres Coffee and Resto, including visitor numbers for the period July–December 2025, as well as from various literature sources, such as textbooks, scientific journals, and scientific publications relevant to the research variables. Secondary data was used to support the empirical analysis and strengthen the research's theoretical foundation.

Measurement Scale

The measurement scale used in this study was a five-point Likert scale, referring to (Sugiyono 2019). The Likert scale was used to measure respondents' attitudes, perceptions, and opinions regarding the research variables. In its use, the neutral category was omitted and replaced with a more assertive attitude category to avoid respondents being in a state of doubt. The measurement scale used consisted of:

- (1) Strongly Disagree, (2) Disagree, (3) Less Agree, (4) Agree and (5) Strongly Agree.
- (2)

Operational Definition of Research Variables and Indicators

The research variables consist of independent variables and dependent variables as follows:

Table 2.
Operational Definition of Research Variables and Indicators

NO	Variables	Definition Operational	Indicator	Scale
1.	Customer Loyalty (Y)	Buyer intent and tendencies For Keep goingshopping for products or services on the company that The same, Wih influenced by the quality of experience Whichgiven, not just prices or promotions. (Rahmayoga and Wiwoho 2025)	1. Intention to revisit 2. Willingness to recommend 3. Makehis Top Choice (Hwang andChoe 2022)	Likert

2.	Product Quality (X1)	Customer perception of the taste, consistency and quality of the products presented by the Vice President <i>Coffee</i> (Hwang and Choe 2022)	1. consistent taste 2. Quality of raw materials 3. Product Presentation (August 2022)	Likert
3	Service Quality (X2)	Customer perception of employee ability to provide service during the service process (Soerjanto, Priyanto, and Rahayu 2024)	1. Employee friendliness 2. Speed of service 3. Professionalism e employees (Soerjanto, Priyanto, and Rahayu 2024)	Likert
4	Price (X3)	Customer perception regarding the suitability between the price paid and the quality of the product and service provided. accepted (Konuk 2021)	1. Affordability 2. Price matches quality 3. Reasonableness of prices compared to competitors (Wijaya and Tjokrosaputro 2024)	Likert
5	Cafe Atmosphere (X4)	Perception customers regarding the comfort of the physical environment of Wapres Coffee (Kim and Lee 2020)	1. Cleanliness 2. Spatial comfort 3. lighting and air circulation (Line and Hanks 2022)	Likert

Research Hypothesis

The hypotheses in this study are formulated as follows: H1: Product quality has a positive effect on customer loyalty. H2: Service quality has a positive effect on customer loyalty. H3: Price has a positive effect on customer loyalty. H4: Cafe atmosphere has a positive effect on customer loyalty. H5: Product quality is the most dominant variable influencing customer loyalty at Wapres Coffee compared to service quality, price, and cafe atmosphere.

Data Analysis Techniques

Data were analyzed using Partial Least Square-based Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) with the help of SmartPLS 3.0 software. PLS-SEM was chosen because it is suitable for models with reflective latent variables and a relatively small sample size. The analysis stages include evaluating the measurement model (outer model) through convergent validity tests (factor loadings and AVE) and discriminant validity (cross loadings), as well as reliability tests (Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability). Next, an evaluation of the structural model (inner model) was carried out through the R^2 value and hypothesis testing using the bootstrapping method. Hypothesis testing was carried out through partial tests (t-tests) to determine the effect of each independent variable on customer loyalty.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Validity Test

This study uses SmartPLS 3.0 to test the validity and reliability of the instrument through convergent validity (factor loading) and discriminant validity (cross loading).

a) Convergent Validity

Convergent validity in the reflective model is assessed based on the loading factor value between the indicator and the construct. An indicator is declared valid if it has a loading factor ≥ 0.70 , although in the initial study a value of 0.50–0.60 was still acceptable. This study uses a limit of ≥ 0.70 with the help of SmartPLS 3.0. The test results can be seen in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1
Results of Instrument Validity Test using loading factor

	Price	Quality service	Product quality	Loyalty Customer	Cafe Atmosphere
X1. 1			0.895		
X1. 2			0.920		
X1. 3			0.903		
X2. 1		0.834			
X2. 2		0.837			
X2. 3		0.861			
X3. 1	0.852				
X3. 2	0.913				
X3. 3	0.891				
X4. 1					0.855
X4. 2					0.938
X4. 3					0.910
Y.1				0.877	
Y.2				0.911	
Y.3				0.887	

Based on Table 3, all loading factor values are > 0.70 , so all indicators are declared valid and suitable for use in research.

b) Discriminant Validity

Following results testing measurement model *discriminant validity* using cross loading can be seen in

Table 4.2
 Results of Instrument Validity Test Using Cross Loading

	Price	Quality service	Quality product	Loyalty Customer	Cafe Atmosphere
X1.1	0.675	0.719	0.895	0.660	0.618
X1.2	0.706	0.725	0.920	0.746	0.657
X1.3	0.703	0.742	0.903	0.741	0.711
X2.1	0.646	0.834	0.660	0.640	0.659
X2.2	0.635	0.837	0.670	0.660	0.633
X2.3	0.680	0.861	0.706	0.637	0.717
X3.1	0.852	0.701	0.631	0.618	0.678
X3.2	0.913	0.654	0.696	0.672	0.701
X3.3	0.891	0.704	0.707	0.739	0.742
X4.1	0.595	0.726	0.575	0.667	0.855
X4.2	0.668	0.692	0.605	0.688	0.938
X4.3	0.702	0.705	0.649	0.743	0.910
Y.1	0.708	0.632	0.633	0.877	0.706
Y.2	0.708	0.726	0.735	0.911	0.697
Y.3	0.637	0.687	0.747	0.887	0.678

Based on Table 4, all indicators have the highest cross loading values in their respective constructs, so they are declared discriminantly valid.

2. Reliability Test

An instrument is declared reliable if it meets the criteria of AVE > 0.50, Cronbach Alpha > 0.60, and Composite Reliability > 0.70. The results of the reliability test are presented in the following table.

Table 4.3
 Calculation of AVE, Cronbach Alpha, and Composite Reliability

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Price	0.863	0.870	0.916	0.785
Quality of service	0.798	0.798	0.881	0.712
Product quality	0.891	0.895	0.932	0.821
Customer Loyalty	0.871	0.873	0.921	0.795
Cafe Atmosphere	0.884	0.888	0.929	0.813

Source: Processed primary data (2026)

Based on Table 5, all variables have a Cronbach Alpha value > 0.60 (Y = 0.871; X1 = 0.891; X2 = 0.798), so they are declared reliable.

3. Structural Model Evaluation (Inner Model)

Evaluation of the inner model can be seen from several indicators, including the coefficient of determination (R²), Predictive Relevance (Q²), and Goodness of Fit Index (GoF) (Hussein, 2015). The results of the structural

model displayed by Smart PLS 3.0 in this study are as follows:

Source: Processed primary data (2025)

Figure 4.1. Structural Inner Model

4. R2 (R-square) results

In assessing a model using PLS, we begin by looking at the R-square for each dependent latent variable. The results of the r2 calculation in this study are as follows.

Table 4.4. Correlation Value (r2)

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Customer Loyalty	0.727	0.715

Source: Processed primary data (2026)

Based on the calculation results using bootstrapping in Table 6 above, the four independent variables (product quality, service quality, price, and cafe atmosphere) together are able to explain 72.7% of the variation in customer loyalty ($R^2 = 0.727$), while the remaining 27.3% is explained by other factors outside this research model.

5. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing in this study used an alpha of 5%, meaning that if the t-statistic value is ≥ 1.960 or the probability value is \leq the level of significance ($\alpha = 5\%$). The 0.05 limit means that the probability of deviation is only 5%, and the remaining 95% indicates that the hypothesis can be accepted.

a) Partial Testing (t-Test)

Direct influence testing is used to explain hypotheses 1, 2, 3, and 4 through path coefficients. The path coefficient value can be seen through the t-statistic value which must be above the t-table, namely 1.96, which means there is an influence of the exogenous variable on the endogenous variable in each predetermined hypothesis. A t-statistic value ≥ 1.960 or a probability value \leq level of significance ($\alpha = 5\%$), has the conclusion that the hypothesis is accepted, namely there is a significant influence between the variables tested. Table 7 shows the results of direct hypothesis testing with bootstrapping in Smart PLS 3.0 software. Below will be explained the explanation of each hypothesis in this study.

Table 4.5
Path Coefficients

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Price -> Loyalty Customer	0.179	0.185	0.146	1,226	0.221
Quality of service -> Loyalty Customer	0.122	0.117	0.122	0.996	0.320
Product quality -> Customer Loyalty	0.351	0.362	0.145	2,429	0.015
Cafe Atmosphere -> Customer Loyalty	0.280	0.269	0.133	2,108	0.036

Based on Table 7, the test results for each hypothesis are as follows:

a. Hypothesis 1

H1: Product quality affects customer loyalty. Based on the test results in Table 7, it can be seen that the t-statistic value of the relationship between variable X1 and variable y is 2.429 with a p-value of 0.015. The test results show that the t-statistic ≥ 1.96 and the sig. value \leq level of significance ($\alpha = 5\%$). Thus, hypothesis 1 is accepted. This indicates that there is a significant influence between variable X1 and variable y. The results of this study are in accordance with research (Agustia 2022) which proves that product quality has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty in culinary businesses. In line with that, (Rahmayoga and Wiwoho 2025) also found that product quality is the main determinant of customer loyalty in the food and beverage industry. Furthermore, (Ferdian, Anuar, and Muhamad Fadzli 2023) in their research in Malaysia found that product quality is the most dominant factor influencing the intention of coffee shop customers to revisit.

b. Hypothesis 2

H2: Service quality influences customer loyalty. Based on the test results in Table 7, it can be seen that the t-statistic value of the relationship between variable X2 and variable Y is 0.996 with a P value of 0.320. The test results indicate that the t-statistic ≤ 1.96 and the sig value \geq level of significance ($\alpha = 5\%$). Thus, hypothesis 2 is rejected. This indicates that there is no significant influence between variable X2 and variable Y. The results of this study are in accordance with research by (Wijaya and Tjokrosaputro 2024) which shows that when product quality and cafe atmosphere have met customer expectations, service quality is not always a dominant factor in determining loyalty. This finding is also in line with (Hwang and Choe 2022) which states that young consumers prioritize core product quality and functional value over service aspects in forming loyalty. This condition can be explained by the characteristics of Wapres Coffee which implements informal and intimate service, so that formal service standards are not the main expectations of Generation Z customers.

c. Hypothesis 3

H3: Price influences customer loyalty. Based on the test results in Table 7, it can be seen that the t-statistic value of the relationship between variable X3 and variable Y is 1.226 with a sig. of **0.221**. The test results show that the t-statistic is ≤ 1.96 and the sig value is \geq level of significance ($\alpha = 5\%$). Thus, hypothesis 3 is rejected. This indicates that there is no significant influence between variable X3 and variable Y. The results of this study are in accordance with research (Wijaya and Tjokrosaputro 2024) which found that price is not a determining factor for customer loyalty when the product quality received meets expectations. In line with that, (Hwang and Choe 2022) stated that young consumers, including generation Z, tend to build loyalty

based on perceived functional value rather than solely based on price considerations. (Konuk 2021) themselves emphasized that the effect of price on loyalty is indirect, namely mediated by perceived value, so that if customers are satisfied with the product quality and cafe atmosphere, perception of price is no longer a dominant consideration in loyalty decisions.

d. Hypothesis 4

H4: Cafe Atmosphere Affects Customer Loyalty Based on the test results in Table 7, it can be seen that the t-statistic value of the relationship between variable X4 and variable Y is 2.108 with a P-value of 0.036. The test results indicate that the t-statistic ≥ 1.96 and the sig. value \leq level of significance ($\alpha = 5\%$). Thus, hypothesis 4 is accepted. This indicates that there is a significant influence between variable X4 and variable Y. The results of this study are in accordance with research (Kim and Lee 2020) which explains that cafe atmosphere can influence customer emotions and contribute to the formation of loyalty, although the influence is contextual. (Line and Hanks 2022) also found that physical environmental elements such as cleanliness, layout, lighting and air circulation significantly influence customer satisfaction and revisit intentions. Furthermore, (Ferdian, Anuar, and Muhamad Fadzli 2023) in their study on coffee shops in Malaysia found that the comfort of the atmosphere of the place is an important determinant of customer satisfaction and loyalty, especially in the young consumer segment.

e. Hypothesis 5

H5: Product quality is the most dominant variable influencing customer loyalty at Wapres Coffee compared to service quality, price, and cafe atmosphere. Based on the table above, it is known that product quality is the most dominant factor in influencing customer loyalty because it has the largest original sample value among other independent variables, namely 0.351 with a statistic of 2.429 and a p-value of 0.015.

CONCLUSION

Conclusion

This study aims to analyze the factors influencing Generation Z customer loyalty at Wapres Coffee, including product quality, service quality, price, and cafe atmosphere. Based on the results of hypothesis testing using PLS-SEM analysis with SmartPLS 3.0, several conclusions can be drawn as follows.

First, product quality has been shown to have a positive and significant effect on Wapres Coffee customer loyalty, with a t-statistic of 2.429 and a p-value of 0.015 (<0.05). This indicates that consistency of taste, quality of raw materials, and product presentation are the main factors that encourage customers to revisit and recommend Wapres Coffee to others. Product quality has also been shown to be the most dominant factor among the four variables studied, with the highest path coefficient of 0.351.

Second, the cafe atmosphere was proven to have a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty with a t-statistic of 2.108 and a p-value of 0.036 (<0.05). The comfort of Wapres Coffee's physical environment, including cleanliness, layout, lighting, and air circulation, was proven to create a pleasant experience for Generation Z customers, thus encouraging them to return.

Third, service quality was not proven to have a significant effect on customer loyalty, with a t-statistic of 0.996 and a p-value of 0.320 (>0.05). This finding indicates that in the context of Wapres Coffee, service aspects such as friendliness, speed, and employee professionalism are not yet the main determining factors in shaping Generation Z customer loyalty.

Fourth, price was not shown to significantly influence customer loyalty, with a t-statistic of 1.226 and a p-value of 0.221 (>0.05). This finding suggests that when product quality meets customer expectations, price is not a dominant factor in the loyalty decisions of Generation Z customers at Wapres Coffee.

Fifth, product quality is proven to be the most dominant variable in influencing customer loyalty compared to other variables. This is evidenced by the highest path coefficient value (original sample) of product quality among all independent variables, which is 0.351, with a t-statistic of 2.429 and a p-value of 0.015. The order of variable dominance based on the path coefficient is product quality (0.351) $>$ cafe atmosphere (0.280) $>$ price (0.179) $>$ service quality (0.122). Thus, hypothesis 5 is accepted, which indicates that product quality is the strongest and most determining factor in shaping the loyalty of generation Z customers at Wapres Coffee.

Overall, the four independent variables (product quality, service quality, price, and cafe atmosphere) were able to explain 72.7% of the variation in customer loyalty ($R^2 = 0.727$), while the remaining 27.3% was influenced by other factors not examined in this study. The main conclusion of this study is that the loyalty of generation Z customers to Wapres Coffee is more determined by the consistent core quality of the product and the comfortable cafe atmosphere, rather than solely by the visual aesthetics, low price, or service quality. This finding provides

practical implications for Wapres Coffee managers to continue to maintain and improve product quality standards and create a comfortable cafe atmosphere as a primary strategy in maintaining customer loyalty.

Suggestion

Based on the results of this study, the authors offer the following recommendations. First, Wapres Coffee management should continue to maintain and improve the consistency of product quality, particularly in terms of taste, raw material quality, and presentation standards, considering that product quality is the most dominant factor in shaping customer loyalty. Second, attention to the comfort of the cafe atmosphere such as cleanliness, layout, and air circulation needs to be continuously improved because it has been proven to contribute significantly to customer loyalty. Third, further research is recommended to consider other variables such as customer satisfaction, perceived value, or brand loyalty that have not been examined in this study, in order to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the factors shaping customer loyalty in the cafe industry.

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